

Title: Short Report: Morphometric Affinity of the Qarunian Early Egyptian Skull Explored With Fordisc 3.0

Key words

Qarunian, canonical variates, Egypt, Fayum, Africa

INTRODUCTION

The find of a single early Egyptian skull associated with the Qarunian industry in the Fayum was reported by Henneberg et al. (1989). It was described as early Neolithic or terminal paleolithic, with a date of around 8000 BP. The Early Neolithic designation is due to the work in the Western Desert which found bones that were “identified as probably domestic cattle associated with sites similar to those in the Fayum...”

The skull is described as female of about 40 years of age. It is anatomically characterized as having a long braincase, broad forehead, broad face, orbits of intermediate height, broad nose and mesognathic face; its dentition did not indicate any special pattern of attrition (Henneberg, et al.1989).

The standard Penrose measure (Penrose, 1954) was used to assess affinities. The comparison series were from “Mesolithic” Wadi Halfa from the Sudan, early series from the Northwest Africa (Capsian-Neolithic, early Capsian, and epipaleolithic Iberomarusian both called Mechta, Tunisian protohistoric) modern Ugandan labelled “Negroid” and recent Australian aboriginals.

The Penrose distances in this instance were “validated” by analyzing the comparative series with Mahalanobis distances. The resultant matrix was similar in pattern to the one generated by the Penrose statistic, thus giving some confidence in the analysis. The skull was found to be most similar in morphometric pattern to the series from Wadi Halfa and recent Ugandans, and more distant from the early Holocene/late Pleistocene material from northwest Africa, including the Capsian Neolithic and “protohistoric” series. Henneberg et al. (1989) state that it is not possible to establish any “purely populational” identity, but only observe the similarity to the Ugandans and Wadi Halfa, and that the skull was more “modern” than the Mechta (Iberomarusian and Capsian) series. It was further observed that the more robust remains from NW Africa grouped together but not with the fairly robust Mesolithic material from Wadi Halfa.

In this study the Qarunian skull was examined using Fordisc 3.0 (Ousley and Jantz 2013) to further examine the finding of its relative similarities to more recent material. Fordisc 3.0 is not being used to attempt to make an identification as in forensics, but rather to explore the pattern exhibited by the cranium in relationship to modern series in the Howells (1973) database in the geographical continuum from tropical Africa to Europe. A cline in morphometric pattern has been noted along this axis (Keita, 2005, 1990). This study is exploratory, but it was hypothesized that the Qarunian skull would be most like the ancient Egyptian skull series, based on geography, followed by the Kenyan series due to its geographical proximity to Uganda and similarity to the series from there in the previous analysis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The comparative material used in this analysis are the African and European series in the Howells database as found in Fordisc 3.0: E series from Gizeh (late dynastic northern Egypt-

EGY), “Bushman” (South Africa-BUSH), Teita (Kenya-TEI), Zulu (South Africa-ZUL), Dogon (Mali-DOG), Berg (Austria-BERG), Zalavar (Hungary-ZAL), Norse (Norway-NOR) (Howells, 1973). The abbreviations are amended with F or M to indicate female or male. The Egyptian series is from late dynastic Egypt (600-300 BCE), the Dogon from around the 13th century AD, the Hungarian medieval, and the others recent.

The variables used were taken from Table 1 in Henneberg et al. (1989) and converted to Howells (1973) terminology. These were ASB, AUB, BBH, DKB, FRC, GOL, NLB, NLH, NPH, OBB, OBH, PAC, XCB and ZYB. These give basic coverage to the craniofacial region. The cranial base was not complete: basion was not available and therefore neither basi-nasion or basi-prosthion were available.

Fordisc 3.0 uses an algorithm for canonical variates (CVA), otherwise called multiple discriminant functions (MDF) to place an individual with a series based on its distance to the nearest groups centroid value in multivariate space. Predefined groups used in CVA group based on relative similarity to each other based on the measurements used in the analysis. These are converted to axes that describe in a reduced space the dimensions of the original variables as a whole; the axes are weighted combination of the original variables (Ashton et al. 1957, Blackith and Reyment 1971, Van Vark 1976, Klecka 1980). The relative nearness and overlap of groups or individuals in the multivariate space is an indication of similarity. In designated affinity studies this similarity is usually interpreted as indicating closer genetic/genealogical relationship. MDF/CVA permits an unknown individual to be submitted to an analysis based on other groups. Given that the groups are predefined this is technically to be called an identification. In theory to make an identification the unknown has to belong to one of the predefined groups, or this must be likely, as in forensic analysis. However, here this approach is used in an exploratory

morphometric fashion where it is known that the unknown could not belong to any of groups. It is important to note that identifying an “unknown” was not the primary purpose of the original discriminant function which was designed for two groups by Fisher (Albrecht 1980), although the seeds of that idea can be found in the original paper (Fisher 1936). In anthropology the descriptive use of MDF analysis (Ashton et al. 1957) has perhaps generally been more important than other uses, including forensics.

Four analyses were performed: 1) males and females from European and African series, 2) females only from European and African series, 3) females and males from African series, and 4) females only from African series. This approach provided a context for similarity and a way to check for the consistency of the results.

RESULTS

In all analyses the Qarunian skull was most similar to the female Teita series from Kenya (Tables 1a,b and 2a,b). The second similarity was with Teita males (Tables 1a, 2a). The next similarity was with Zulu males and females. Similarity with the late dynastic northern Egyptian series was not great.

DISCUSSION

The relative similarity of the Qarunian skull to the Teita considered with the results from Henneberg et al. (1989) may indicate an adaptive pattern that was common along the Nile and its basin. More than this cannot be said. In the Penrose analysis the skull was most similar to a “Mesolithic” Wadi Halfa and recent Ugandan series which are also from in eastern Africa, in contrast to the Maghreb cranial series of any age. Uganda is adjacent to Kenya which suggests that a study of large series from this region would be of interest in a comparison with series north

and south of the lake regions of east Africa. A more detailed analysis is needed to determine what metric traits most “drive” the similarity between all of these series. Northeastern African populations are known to have morphometric patterns that roughly follow a north-south gradient for multiple aspects of the craniofacial region (Keita, 2004).

Table 1a. Multigroup “Classification” of Current Case (African and European males and females)

Group	Classified into	Distance From	Probabilities Posterior	Typ F	Typ Chi	Typ R	
BERF		32.0	0.000	0.100	0.004	0.000	(54/54)
BERM		39.2	0.000	0.032	0.000	0.000	(57/57)
BUSF		27.2	0.005	0.209	0.018	0.000	(50/50)
BUSM		21.1	0.098	0.485	0.098	0.286	(30/42)
DOGF		34.7	0.000	0.073	0.002	0.000	(53/53)
DOGM		28.2	0.003	0.202	0.013	0.021	(47/48)
EGYF		41.6	0.000	0.027	0.000	0.000	(54/54)
EGYM		40.4	0.000	0.024	0.000	0.000	(59/59)
NORF		31.6	0.001	0.097	0.005	0.000	(56/56)
NORM		31.2	0.001	0.103	0.005	0.000	(56/56)
TEIF	**TEIF**	17.3	0.650	0.574	0.239	0.196	(41/51)
TEIM		19.4	0.228	0.660	0.149	0.353	(22/34)
ZALF		32.4	0.000	0.137	0.004	0.000	(46/46)
ZALM		34.9	0.000	0.068	0.002	0.000	(54/54)
ZULF		26.1	0.008	0.262	0.025	0.021	(46/47)
ZULM		26.5	0.007	0.192	0.023	0.054	(53/56)

Current Case is closest to Teita females

Table 1b. Multigroup “Classification” of Current Case (African and European females)

Group	Classified into	Distance from	Probabilities Posterior	Typ F	Typ Chi	Typ R	
BERF		33.1	0.000	0.076	0.002	0.000	(54/54)
BUSF		28.9	0.005	0.171	0.011	0.020	(49/50)
DOGF		36.9	0.000	0.054	0.001	0.000	(53/53)
EGYF		42.7	0.000	0.023	0.000	0.000	(54/54)
NORF		32.3	0.001	0.088	0.004	0.000	(56/56)
TEIF	**TEIF**	18.2	0.984	0.530	0.196	0.196	(41/51)
ZALF		33.4	0.000	0.122	0.003	0.000	(46/46)
ZULF		27.5	0.010	0.226	0.017	0.043	(45/47)

Current case is closest to Teita females

Table 2a. Multigroup “Classification” of Current Case (African males and females)

Group	Classified into	Distance from	Probabilities Posterior	Typ F	Typ Chi	Typ R	
BUSF		25.6	0.006	0.252	0.029	0.040	(48/50)
BUSM		19.7	0.125	0.545	0.141	0.310	(29/42)
DOGF		32.8	0.000	0.094	0.003	0.000	(53/53)
DOGM		25.4	0.007	0.275	0.031	0.083	(44/48)
EGYF		40.7	0.000	0.031	0.000	0.000	(54/54)
EGYM		39.6	0.000	0.027	0.000	0.000	(59/59)
TEIF	**TEIF**	16.4	0.632	0.619	0.288	0.255	(38/51)
TEIM		18.7	0.206	0.688	0.178	0.382	(21/34)
ZULF		24.5	0.011	0.311	0.040	0.043	(45/47)
ZULM		24.4	0.012	0.248	0.041	0.054	(53/56)

Current Case is closest to Teita females

Table 2b. Multigroup “Classification” of Current Case (African females)

Group	Classified into	Distance from	Probabilities Posterior	Typ F	Typ Chi	Typ R	
BUSF		27.9	0.010	0.195	0.015	0.060	(47/50)
DOGF		36.0	0.000	0.062	0.001	0.000	(53/53)
EGYF		42.7	0.000	0.024	0.000	0.000	(54/54)
TEIF	**TEIF**	18.8	0.967	0.504	0.173	0.235	(39/51)
ZULF		26.3	0.022	0.256	0.023	0.043	(45/47)

Current Case is closest to Teita females

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